

THE EFFECT OF ELASTIC CORE ON THE STABILITY OF COMPOSITE CIRCULAR CYLINDRICAL SHELLS

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SUMMARY: The effect of an elastic core on the thin laminated circular cylindrical shells subjected to uniform axial compression, lateral pressure is analyzed. Moreover, the solution methodology is described, and results are generated for the composite circular cylindrical shells with an elastic core. The results have shown that the material behavior of the core and the boundary conditions of shell have a great effect on stability . The method appears to be worth recommending , especially while designing solid engines.

KEYWORDS: composite material , structural stability , finite difference theory

INTRODUCTION

Circular cylindrical shells find wide uses in complicated aerospace structural systems. Especially, in the recent few years, the constant demand for lightweight efficient structures, led the structural engineers to the use of composite materials. One of the keys of the correct and effective use of these composite shells is to find a good method to analyze the stability of the shells.

In 1975, Tennyson[1] made a review of previous studies on the buckling of laminated cylinders. Several papers were involved in the comparison of the efficiency and accuracy between Flugge's linear shell theory and other shell theories (such as the theory based on Donnell's equations). In the past, the inverse method or energy method [1,2] was widely used to analyzed the shell stability; in the recent, Simitses[3] adopted Galerkin-difference method to analyze the stability of the laminated circular cylindrical shells subjected to axial compression and torsion, and got good results. This method is especially suitable for middle-short shells (length/radius $\ll 5$).

The stability analysis of metallic circular cylindrical shells with a soft elastic core under axial compression and lateral pressure began in the end of nineteen-fifties[4]. As for the stability research of laminated circular cylindrical shells with an elastic core under axial compression and lateral pressure is very few.

In this paper, the effect of an elastic core on the stability of laminated circular cylindrical shells subjected to axial compression and lateral pressure is analyzed. The Galerkin-difference method is used to solve the modified Donnell's equations. Then, in terms of the stability criterion, the critical loads can be found. The effect of the core is determined by the elastic constant of the core[4]. For convenience, the following assumptions are introduced : 1.

Neglect the shear between the elastic core surface and the inner wall of the shell; 2. The normal displacement of the shell middle surface is equal to the core surface's; 3. The core is isotropic, solid and linear. In general, if the ratio of the inner diameter and the external diameter exceeds 0.55, to simplify the core as solid causes very small errors[4]; 4. Each lamina of the shells is orthotropic.

MATHEMATICAL FORMULATION

The geometry and reference frame are shown on Fig.1. Reference surface is the middle surface.

Fig.1. Geometry

The kinematic relations are

$$\begin{aligned}
 \epsilon_{xx} &= \epsilon_{xx}^0 - zk_{xx} \\
 \epsilon_{yy} &= \epsilon_{yy}^0 - zk_{yy} \\
 \epsilon_{xy} &= \epsilon_{xy}^0 - 2zk_{xy} \\
 \epsilon_{xx}^0 &= u_{,x} + w^2_{,x} / 2 \\
 \epsilon_{yy}^0 &= v_{,y} - w / R + w^2_{,y} / 2 \\
 \epsilon_{xy}^0 &= u_{,y} + v_{,x} + w_{,x} w_{,y}
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{1}$$

where

and $k_{xx} = w_{,xx} ; k_{yy} = w_{,yy} ; k_{xy} = w_{,xy} .$

Note that w is the normal displacement of the middle surface, which is positive when moving to the inner, u and v are the displacement components in the middle surface, and $\epsilon_{xx}^0, \epsilon_{yy}^0, \epsilon_{xy}^0$ and k_{xx}, k_{yy}, k_{xy} the middle surface stretching and bending strains.

In this paper, we consider single-direction composite materials. Each lamina is orthotropic and the constitutive equations are

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_{xx} \\ \sigma_{yy} \\ \sigma_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{E_{11}}{1-\mu_{12}\mu_{21}} & \frac{\mu_{21}E_{11}}{1-\mu_{12}\mu_{21}} & 0 \\ \frac{\mu_{12}E_{22}}{1-\mu_{12}\mu_{21}} & \frac{E_{22}}{1-\mu_{12}\mu_{21}} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & G \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_{xx} \\ \varepsilon_{yy} \\ \varepsilon_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} Q_{xx} & Q_{xy} & 0 \\ Q_{yx} & Q_{yy} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & Q_{ss} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_{xx} \\ \varepsilon_{yy} \\ \varepsilon_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

where E_{11} and E_{22} are longitudinal and transverse Young's moduli respectively,

$\mu_{12} = -\frac{\varepsilon_{yy}}{\varepsilon_{xx}}$ and $\mu_{21} = -\frac{\varepsilon_{xx}}{\varepsilon_{yy}}$ are the Poisson's ratio, and G is the shear modulus. In engineering, the fiber direction has an angle with the axial line of the cylindrical shell. Its constitutive equations [5] are :

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_{xx} \\ \sigma_{yy} \\ \sigma_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} Q_{11} & Q_{21} & Q_{16} \\ Q_{21} & Q_{22} & Q_{26} \\ Q_{61} & Q_{62} & Q_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_{xx} \\ \varepsilon_{yy} \\ \varepsilon_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} Q_{11} &= m^4 Q_{xx} + n^4 Q_{yy} + 2m^2 n^2 Q_{xy} + 4m^2 n^2 Q_{ss} \\ Q_{22} &= n^4 Q_{xx} + m^4 Q_{yy} + 2m^2 n^2 Q_{xy} + 4m^2 n^2 Q_{ss} \\ Q_{21} &= m^2 n^2 Q_{xx} + m^2 n^2 Q_{yy} + (m^4 + n^4) Q_{xy} - 4m^2 n^2 Q_{ss} \\ Q_{66} &= m^2 n^2 (Q_{xx} + Q_{yy}) - 2m^2 n^2 Q_{xy} + (m^2 - n^2)^2 Q_{ss} \\ Q_{61} &= Q_{16} = m^3 n Q_{xx} - m n^3 Q_{yy} + (m n^3 - m^3 n) Q_{xy} + 2(m n^3 - m^3 n) Q_{ss} \\ Q_{62} &= Q_{26} = m n^3 Q_{xx} - m^3 n Q_{yy} + (m^3 n - m n^3) Q_{xy} + 2(m^3 n - m n^3) Q_{ss} \end{aligned}$$

where $m = \cos\theta$, $n = \sin\theta$, ply angle θ is positive in counterclockwise direction.

Now we introduce stress and moment resultants,

$$\begin{Bmatrix} N_{xx} \\ N_{yy} \\ N_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} = \int \begin{bmatrix} h_n \sigma_{xx} \\ \sigma_{yy} \\ h_0 \sigma_{xy} \end{bmatrix} dz \quad (4)$$

and

$$\begin{Bmatrix} M_{xx} \\ M_{yy} \\ M_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} = \int z \begin{bmatrix} h_n \sigma_{xx} \\ \sigma_{yy} \\ h_0 \sigma_{xy} \end{bmatrix} dz \quad (5)$$

Use of the principle of the stationary value of the total potential yields the transverse equilibrium equation of laminated cylindrical shell with an elastic core :

$$M_{xx,xx} + 2M_{yx,yx} + M_{yy,yy} + N_{xx} w_{,xx} + N_{yy} \left(\frac{1}{R} + w_{,yy} \right) + 2N_{xy} w_{,xy} + q - p = 0 \quad (6)$$

where q is the lateral pressure, p is core's reaction force ($p = f_{mn} w$), and the core's elastic constant f_{mn} is seen in reference[4]. The compatibility equation is :

$$\varepsilon_{xx,yy}^0 + \varepsilon_{yy,xx}^0 - \varepsilon_{xy,xy}^0 = -\frac{1}{R}w_{,xx} + w_{,xy}^2 - w_{,yy}w_{,xx} \quad (7)$$

Here we do not consider the torsion. Introduction of stress function F , defined below, leads to the identical satisfaction of the two in-plane equilibrium equations.

$$N_{xx} = -N_{xx}^0 + F_{,yy}, N_{yy} = N_{yy}^0 + F_{,xx}, N_{xy} = -F_{,xy} \quad (8)$$

The transverse equilibrium equation and in-plane compatibility equation then can be written solely in terms of F and w respectively, or

$$\begin{aligned} L_1(F) + L_2(w) + F_{,xx} \left(\frac{1}{R} + w_{,yy} \right) + N_{yy}^0 \left(\frac{1}{R} + w_{,yy} \right) + F_{,yy}w_{,xx} - N_{xx}^0 w_{,xx} - 2F_{,xy}w_{,xy} + q - f_{mn}w = 0 \\ L_3(F) + L_1(w) + \frac{1}{R}w_{,xx} - w_{,xy}^2 + w_{,xx}w_{,yy} = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} L_1(F) &= b_{21}F_{,xxxx} + (-b_{31} + 2b_{23})F_{,xxxy} + (b_{11} - 2b_{33} + b_{22})F_{,xxyy} + (-b_{32} + 2b_{13})F_{,xyyy} + b_{12}F_{,yyyy}; \\ L_2(w) &= d_{11}w_{,xxxx} + (2d_{13} + 2d_{31})w_{,xxxy} + (d_{12} + 4d_{33} + d_{21})w_{,xxyy} + (2d_{32} + 2d_{33})w_{,xyyy} + d_{22}w_{,yyyy}; \\ L_3(F) &= a_{11}F_{,yyyy} - 2a_{13}F_{,xyyy} + (2a_{12} + a_{33})F_{,xxyy} - 2a_{23}F_{,xxxy} + a_{22}F_{,xxxx}; \\ [a_{ij}] &= [A_{ij}]^{-1}, [b_{ij}] = [a_{ij}][B_{ij}], [d_{ij}] = [B_{ij}][b_{ij}] - [D_{ij}], [A_{ij}] = \sum_{k=1}^N Q_{ij}^{(k)}(h_k - h_{k-1}), \\ [B_{ij}] &= \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=1}^N Q_{ij}^{(k)}(h_k^2 - h_{k-1}^2), [D_{ij}] = \frac{1}{3} \sum_{k=1}^N Q_{ij}^{(k)}(h_k^3 - h_{k-1}^3); \end{aligned}$$

and N is the ply numbers. When conducting linear stability analysis of the circular cylindrical shells with an elastic core, we can neglect the nonlinear items of the above equations. Let the shell be critical state, then $F = F_c + \Delta F$, $w = w_c + \Delta w$ (10)

where sublabel c represents critical state, and $\Delta F, \Delta w$ are any small value. Put (10) into equilibrium and compatibility equations, we get the linear Donnell's equation, or

$$\begin{aligned} L_1(\Delta F) + L_2(\Delta w) - N_{xx}^0 \Delta w_{,xx} + \frac{1}{R} \Delta F_{,xx} + N_{yy}^0 \Delta w_{,yy} - f_{mn} \Delta w = 0 \\ L_3(\Delta F) + L_1(\Delta w) + \frac{\Delta w_{,xx}}{R} = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

SOLUTION METHODOLOGY

Let ΔF and Δw have the following forms:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta F(x, y) &= \sum_{i=1}^p [C_i(x) \cos \frac{iny}{R} + D_i(x) \sin \frac{iny}{R}] \\ \Delta w(x, y) &= \sum_{i=1}^p [A_i(x) \cos \frac{iny}{R} + B_i(x) \sin \frac{iny}{R}] \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

where n is the circumferential wave numbers, p is the items of the trigonometric series, and A_i, B_i, C_i, D_i are unknown function about x . Put (12) into (11), adopt Galerkin-difference method, we can reduce (11) into linear equations, or

$$\left\{ \frac{1}{\Delta x^2} \begin{bmatrix} M_3 & M_1 \\ -I & 0 \end{bmatrix} + \frac{1}{2\Delta x} \begin{bmatrix} M_4 & M_2 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \right\} \{\beta_i\}_{j+1} + \left\{ \begin{bmatrix} M_5 & 0 \\ 0 & I \end{bmatrix} - \frac{2}{\Delta x^2} \begin{bmatrix} M_3 & M_1 \\ -I & 0 \end{bmatrix} \right\} \{\beta_i\}_j \quad (13)$$

$$+ \left\{ \frac{1}{\Delta x^2} \begin{bmatrix} M_3 & M_1 \\ -I & 0 \end{bmatrix} - \frac{1}{2\Delta x} \begin{bmatrix} M_4 & M_2 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \right\} \{\beta_i\}_{j-1} = 0$$

where $\{\beta_i\} = [x_i \ \eta_i]^T$, $\{\eta_i\} = \{x_i\}_{,xx}$, $\{x_i\} = [A_i \ B_i \ C_i \ D_i]^T$, $i=1,2, \dots, p$, $j=1,2, \dots, NP$, NP is the mesh points, I is the 4×4 identity matrix, and M_1, M_2, \dots, M_5 are 4×4 matrices with known elements. This is a set of $8p \times NP$ linear algebraic equations with $8p(NP+2)$ unknown variables. According to stability criterion, set $\{\beta_i\} \neq 0$, through the use of that the factor determinant value of (13) is zero, we can find the critical loads.

As the same, we can reduce (11) into standard characteristic equations, that is

$$\left\{ \frac{1}{\Delta x^2} \begin{bmatrix} M_3' & M_1 \\ -I & 0 \end{bmatrix} + \frac{1}{2\Delta x} \begin{bmatrix} M_4 & M_2 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \right\} \{\beta_i\}_{j+1} + \left\{ \begin{bmatrix} M_5' & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} - \frac{2}{\Delta x^2} \begin{bmatrix} M_3' & M_1 \\ -I & 0 \end{bmatrix} \right\} \{\beta_i\}_j + \quad (14)$$

$$\left\{ \frac{1}{\Delta x^2} \begin{bmatrix} M_3' & M_1 \\ -I & 0 \end{bmatrix} - \frac{1}{2\Delta x} \begin{bmatrix} M_4 & M_2 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \right\} \{\beta_i\}_{j-1} = \frac{N_{xx}^0}{\Delta x^2} \begin{bmatrix} F_1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \{\beta_i\}_{j+1} + \frac{N_{xx}^0}{\Delta x^2} \begin{bmatrix} F_1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \{\beta_i\}_{j-1}$$

$$+ \left\{ N_{yy}^0 \begin{bmatrix} F_2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} - N_{xx}^0 \frac{2}{\Delta x^2} \begin{bmatrix} F_1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \right\} \{\beta_i\}_j$$

where $[M_3']$, $[M_5']$, $[F_1]$, $[F_2]$ are 4×4 matrices with known elements. (14) and typical characteristic equation $[E]\{\beta\} = P[G]\{\beta\}$ are the same. If let $[C] = [E]^{-1}[G]$, then the equation can be modified as $[C]\{\beta\} = \frac{1}{P}\{\beta\}$, which we can get the critical values by using the multiply-index method.

EXAMPLES AND DISCUSSION

Stability of Laminated Circular Cylindrical Shells

The critical loads of 3-ply Boron/Epoxy circular cylindrical shells

The material properties are:

$$E_{11} = 0.27586 \times 10^6 \text{ N/mm}^2, \mu_{12} = 0.25, E_{22} = 0.31034 \times 10^6 \text{ N/mm}^2,$$

$$\mu_{21} = 0.028, G = 0.10345 \times 10^5 \text{ N/mm}^2$$

The geometry configuration is $R=152.4\text{mm}$, $L=304.8\text{mm}$ and the total thickness $t=0.9144\text{mm}$. The stacking combinations of angle-ply are listed below, which are $\theta/\theta/0^\circ$ from the outside to inside. The boundary condition is SS-2. The results are seen in Table 1. As we see from Table 1, the results of this paper are approximate to the references'.

The critical loads of Graphite/Epoxy laminated cylindrical shells subjected axial compressure

The material properties are:

$$E_{11} = 0.11999 \times 10^6 N/mm^2, E_{22} = 0.76985 \times 10^5 N/mm^2,$$

$$\mu_{12} = 0.32, \mu_{21} = 0.02051, G = 0.48758 \times 10^4 N/mm^2,$$

The R=100mm, L=200mm, and the stacking combinations are (1) N=3, 90°/-20°/20°, t=0.419mm; (2) N=4, 90°/-45°/-45°/0°, t=0.579mm; (3) N=6, 90°/90°/30°/-30°/-30°/30°, t=0.899mm. The boundary condition is CC-4. The results are seen in Table 2.

The Stability of Laminated Circular Cylindrical Shell with Elastic Core

The critical loads of (3) group shell in 1.2 above with an elastic core under lateral and hydrostatic pressure are listed in Table 3, where the core's $E_c = 4.8275 N/mm^2$

Table 1 ($N_{cr}; N$)

source	θ N_{cr}	10°	20°	30°	40°	50°	60°	70°	80°
[6]		160.21 (11)	195.09 (12)	223.64 (12)	229.07 (12)	211.91 (12)	189.31 (12)	166.69 (12)	147.65 (11)
[7]		159.02 (11)	189.84 (12)	212.26 (12)	221.01 (12)	210.68 (12)	172.78 (12)	143.66 (12)	128.41 (11)
this paper		151.12 (10)	184.90 (13)	208.13 (12)	212.78 (14)	210.34 (12)	173.92 (12)	147.55 (11)	134.46 (10)

Table 2 (N/mm)

source	(1)	(2)	(3)
test	21.114(10)	43.513(8)	146.628(-)
Simitses[3] calculation	23.438--26.478(12)	40.60--63.45(9)	138.86--165.64(9)
this paper calculation	26.14(14)	50.031(12)	160.84(10)

Table 3 ($P_{cr} : 10^{-2} N/mm^2$)

load and boundary condition	μ_c P_{cr}	0.35	0.4	0.45	0.5
lateral pressure SS-1		49.309(9)	50.668(9)	52.358(9)	54.461(9)
hydrostatic pressure SS-1		47.703(9)	48.889(10)	50.358(10)	52.185(10)
lateral pressure CC-4		52.061	53.35(10)	54.944(10)	56.923(10)

In addition to the examples listed above, the critical lateral pressures of two group of composite shells with elactic core under different E_c , boundary conditions, angle-ply and numbers of laminate are calculated. The calculated results show that the core's E_c and boundary condition have great effect on the critical loads, the angle-ply θ has little effect and under thickness unchanged the numbers of laminate have no effect on the critical loads.

CONCLUSION

This paper uses Galerkin-difference method to reduce the Donnell's partial differential equations of laminated cylindrical shell with elastic core to linear equations. Then according to the stability criterion, the critical loads are found by using the multiply-index method to solve the characteristic equations. The FORTRAN program has been programmed, which can be used to calculate critical loads under different cases. The results of examples show that the method adopted in this paper is reliable and has great value to the designing engineers.

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